

MECHANISMS FOR TEACHING CLINICAL SCIENCES IN THE E-LEARNING ENVIRONMENT IN MEDICAL HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract. *This article discusses the importance of creating an electronic environment, the use of information and communication and pedagogical technologies in teaching Clinical Sciences in medical higher education institutions. The article will talk about electronic educational technologies, information and pedagogical technologies, their application to the educational process.*

Keywords: *medical education, future doctors, information technology, electronic education technology, electronic education environment, communication, integrated education, switching, electronic resources.*

Introduction. Modernization of national medical education in our country, introduction of international educational standards in this field, conducting comprehensive scientific research on current problems of public health protection, as well as an effective system of providing spiritual and moral education to young people who are studying consistent measures are being realized in our country.

Various definitions and different opinions have been given by scientists about the electronic learning environment, and we will introduce some of them below. The e-learning environment can be described as follows. The e-learning environment is considered as a set of interrelated conditions that ensure, on the one hand, human education, and on the other hand, the formation of an electronic and creatively thinking teacher personality. Electronic learning environment is the use of new technologies, methods and tools to make the educational process more effective and modern. An innovative learning environment is one that is able to evolve and adapt as educational practices evolve and change, with a focus on the future. E-learning environments support strengths-based teaching and learning. It provides flexibility, independence, ubiquity and interdependence to students and teachers. Aspects of traditional and electronic education are becoming integrated in terms of certain features. Electronic education serves to increase the quality and opportunities of education by using an innovative approach to education, including multimedia and Internet technologies. Taking this into account, it can be considered that electronic education allows students to acquire knowledge in a conveniently organized environment. The development of e-learning methodology requires the creation of e-learning distance courses in a systematic approach in accordance with educational programs, the acquisition of modern knowledge and views using innovative educational technologies.

Research Methodology. Our research shows that in the modern environment of e-learning platforms, the governments of different countries are investing a lot in the scientific field, especially in research and innovation. For example, Germany spends about 2.7% of its GDP on research and development, the USA - 2.8%, and Japan - about 3.5%. Countries with economies in transition are much less: Belarus spends 0.74% of GDP, Russia - 1.04% [220]. Countries such as

Germany, the USA, Sweden, South Korea, and China occupy the top places in the world in terms of the use of electronic educational technologies in the educational process. We can see that Russia is in 47th place among the countries of the Commonwealth of Independent States, while Uzbekistan is in 82nd place based on the data of 2022. US universities have organizationally very flexible structures and play a very important role in maintaining the high level of innovation of the socio-economic and educational environment of their countries. The use of virtual reality systems in the educational process - learning with the help of VR is carried out by the presence of the student in a virtual environment. This allows you to do different types of activities during the learning process. First of all, it concerns the organization of working together with more realism. Virtual reality also provides the necessary skills to work with a variety of objects with the "right to make mistakes" that encourages students to explore the virtual and real world. AR technology (augmented reality) places content in digital format in the real user environment. Information can be in the form of text, images, video, audio and 3D models. As a rule, light glasses with a projector or a cell phone camera are used for it. MR (Mixed Reality) technology is the coexistence of VR and AR, creating a hybrid reality. The headset scans the surrounding world, recognizes objects and creates 3D models of them, which allows you to interact with the real world through the virtual world. It engages students in the learning process, allows them to practice skills, solve problems and apply knowledge to the world around them, which improves the dynamics of learning and prepares students for the future. The rate of change in science, technology and innovation today is very high, and it is almost impossible to ensure the effectiveness of educational activities without carrying out fast and competent monitoring. Ensuring the sustainable development of educational activities, increasing the competitiveness of personnel by expanding the innovative educational environment, developing long-term forecasting methods based not only on current trends, but also on the basis of educational and technological advances that may occur in the future, are related to the need to use foresight [232]. Foresight means looking into the future. It refers to activities aimed at the far future in terms of promoting innovation, activating strategic evaluation, and research and development. The long-term cooperative action coordination (FOREN Guede) is distinguished by achievements in a specific field of scientific research for example, IBM is using Watson, an emerging form of intelligent systems, to advise students 24 hours a day, 365 days a year at Deakin University in Australia. According to the scientists who conducted research on innovations, the classification of pedagogical innovations is classified as the following types of activities: validity period, environment of changes, scope of use, sources of emergence, methods of implementation.

Conclusion. In conclusion, we can say that e-learning platforms combine traditional learning practices with game mechanics. This allows students to make the curriculum more interactive and interesting. Serious games, on the other hand, follow a typical game structure to align the student with specific objects and goals.

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